

LLM-Guided Reinforcement Learning for Adaptive Inter-Slice Resource Prioritization in 6G O-RAN

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Abstract—The growing complexity of next-generation networks makes intelligent and adaptive management essential for Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN)-based network slicing. Traditional Reinforcement Learning (RL) solutions in xApps automate resource allocation but struggle to incorporate high-level operator intents into their optimization process. To address this limitation, we propose a Large Language Model (LLM)-guided RL framework that bridges the gap between human intent and autonomous network control. In this approach, the LLM-based agent in the rApp interprets operator prompts and contextual network information to dynamically adjust the reward function of the RL agent operating in the xApp, ensuring that resource allocation decisions across slices reflect strategic objectives. The simulation results show that the proposed LLM-guided RL approach achieves higher cumulative reward while maintaining closer alignment with the operator objectives, creating the basis for more intelligent and dynamic O-RAN management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Next-generation Beyond-5G or 6G networks will support heterogeneous services and technologies, operate with high flexibility and agility, and enable rapid deployment while dynamically adapting to changing traffic demands. To address these requirements, the O-RAN Alliance takes initiatives to define standards and interfaces for Open RAN systems, including AI-driven orchestration and disaggregation of RAN components [1]. It introduces the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC), which enables both near-real-time (near-RT) and non-real-time (non-RT) control and orchestration of the RAN through software modules, called respectively xApps and rApps. To meet diverse service-level requirements and ensure end-to-end service quality, O-RAN enables network slicing [2], [3]. Furthermore, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) natively into the O-RAN network enhances autonomy, efficiency, and adaptability in use cases ranging from resource allocation to anomaly detection and security management [4]. Recent research shows that RL has gained particular attention, where RL agents learn optimal decision-making policies through continuous interaction with the environment, receiving rewards or penalties based on their actions [5]. In wireless networks, RL has demonstrated a strong potential for adaptive resource allocation, interference mitigation, and load balancing, contributing to the achievement of network goals of improved agility and efficiency. Research has explored the integration of RL within

the O-RAN architecture, for example, focusing on the resource allocation solution for bandwidth optimization [6] and minimizing violation of Service Level Agreements (SLA) [7] in network slicing scenarios. In [8], deep-RL approaches have been used for efficient slicing and scheduling control policies, while [9] offered a deep-RL-based solution for Quality of Service (QoS)-aware intra-slice resource allocation in the O-RAN. In parallel, the rapid development of LLMs has introduced new capabilities for context understanding, reasoning, and natural language interpretation [10]. These models can process complex textual information and extract actionable insights, enabling them to interpret operator intent or analyze network data to assist in decision-making. Recent works have also explored LLM applications in wireless communications, such as resource allocation [11] and base station placement [12]. Beyond the O-RAN domain, several works have studied the cooperation between RL and LLMs in other application areas, demonstrating how LLMs can guide RL agents through natural language reasoning and reward shaping. Such as [13] which proposed a pipeline that uses GPT-4 to translate human-readable task descriptions into structured reward functions in robotic manipulation; or in autonomous driving [14] where a closed-loop framework that leverages LLM to automatically generate and optimize reward functions reduced the complexity and time costs associated with manual design. Despite these advances, a fundamental challenge persists in the telecommunication domain: automating the translation of human intents, expressed in natural language, into actionable network management decisions. In O-RAN slicing, LLMs can leverage intent-based commands to guide adjustments to an RL agent's reward function, enabling autonomous resource allocation. They can also act as stand-alone intelligent entities, supporting decision-making and coordination by incorporating contextual observations and historical optimization data, as demonstrated in [15] for efficient and adaptive resource orchestration. Addressing this open problem represents a critical step towards achieving human-aligned, self-optimizing, and thus, knowledgeable O-RAN management. In this regard, recent research works on RL with LLMs offer encouraging pathways towards intent-driven automation [16], where LLMs can enhance RL agents at different stages of their workflow, for instance, by

improving policy interpretation, generating synthetic training data, or guiding exploration, and shaping rewards to align with high-level objectives. [17] introduced a hierarchical RIC framework to improve collaboration between RICs in O-RAN, highlighting the effectiveness of combining LLM-empowered to provide guidance in non-RT RIC and RL-empowered to exploit this guidance with local observation in near-RT RIC to tackle dynamic and complex resource management. Moreover, in [18], [19] they used LLMs to give deep-RL a more meaningful state representation, enabling adaptive decision-making that optimizes QoS and resource allocation.

Unlike previous works, our approach does not rely on LLMs merely for state enhancement [18], [19] or power optimization [17] in O-RAN. Instead, it leverages the LLM’s reasoning capability to interpret human intent and incorporate global network insights to dynamically configure the RL agent’s reward function. This enables the RL agent to prioritize and allocate resources across slices in an adaptive and intent-aware manner, aligning high-level operator objectives with low-level network control. Overall, the novelty of this paper lies in integrating LLMs with RL for intent-driven resource prioritization for network slicing in O-RAN.

A. Contributions

This paper presents an approach for allocating Physical Resource Blocks (PRB) to different slices within a Base Station (BS), exploiting the capability of an LLM to interpret the intent of an operator and use it to shape the reward via weights during RL training, thus enabling an effective and autonomous intelligent O-RAN. In detail:

- The RL agent, deployed as an xApp, operates in near-RT RIC to predict and manage PRB allocation across slices, while the LLM, implemented as an rApp, handles intent management in a non-RT RIC.
- During each iteration, the RL agent receives down-link Key Performance Metrics (KPMs) from the BS, connected to multiple User Equipments (UEs), and determines the corresponding allocation action for each slice.
- When the operator updates the slice priority, the LLM interprets this intent and applies the corresponding reward-shaping adjustments, allowing the RL agent to adapt its allocation policy accordingly.
- The results show that the proposed LLM-guided RL approach enhances adaptability and alignment with the operator prioritization goals.

II. PROPOSED SOLUTION

The architecture of the O-RAN for the proposed solution is depicted in Fig. 1.

This paper presents an approach that dynamically allocates resources, specifically PRBs, between a critical Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC) slice, a best-effort enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) slice, and a massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC) slice

Fig. 1: Proposed architecture, including the RL Agent (xApp) and the LLM (rApp), with the interactions through the various interfaces between RICs and E2 Node.

within a BS. The aim is to ensure low latency for URLLC while maximizing throughput of eMBB and maximizing number of transmitted packets in mMTC, with inter-slice priorities set by an operator. The proposed architecture integrates an RL agent as an xApp within Near-RT RIC, enabling operation within the 10-1000 ms control loop for the distribution of PRBs; and an LLM which is deployed as an rApp in the Non-RT RIC, operating at time scales above 1 s to provide high-level policy guidance to the RL agent. These control loops are consistent with the O-RAN specifications for the Non-RT and Near-RT RIC functionalities. The overall interaction can be viewed as a hierarchical control system in which the LLM interprets natural language instructions from the operator, such as "Prioritize URLLC traffic", together with global information, in particular previous slice weights and aggregated KPMs of UEs from the O-RAN environment through the O1 interface, and processes these inputs to generate quantitative control signals in the form of slice priority weights, which are transmitted to the Near-RT RIC via the A1 interface. The RL agent then uses these weights, combined with real-time per-slice KPMs collected from the E2 Node through the E2 interface, to perform fine-grained, real-time PRB allocation among slices. Eventually, these allocation decisions are sent to the E2 Node through the E2 interface ready to be implemented.

Given the limited computational resources available, a key challenge is that the training is carried out on an offline dataset [20], which means that the agent does not interact directly with an environment but uses the logs of a retrieved policy to fit a new one.

A. Dataset

The dataset (named CoLORAN) used is an extensive data collection of experiments on Colosseum retrieved from this paper [21]. The large-scale Radio Frequency scenario emulates a real-world cellular deployment in Rome, Italy, with the positions of the BSs derived from the OpenCellID database. They instantiated a softwarized cellular network with 7 BSs, each serving 6 users for a total of 42 UEs equally divided among the 3 slices. In their data collection campaign, they

TABLE I: Dataset Settings

Parameter	Value
Number of BS	$N_{BS} = 7$
Number of UE per BS	$N_{UE} = 42$
Number of Slices	$N_{SL} = 3$
Slices, n	eMBB, mMTC, URLLC (2 UEs/BS/slice)

gathered 3.4 GB of data, for a total of more than 73 hours of experiments, in which the BSs periodically report RAN KPMs to the non-RT RIC. The most relevant details for the scenario are presented in Table I.

B. System Model

In this subsection, we define the tuple (S, A, R, S') (state, action, reward, next state) for our proposed RL setup based on the characteristics of the collected dataset.

a) States: At each decision step, the agent observes the downlink KPMs from the CoLORAN dataset, aggregated per slice across all UEs in each BS, representing the overall slice-level network conditions. Considered downlink KPMs are the following:

- dl_mcs: downlink modulation and coding scheme
- dl_n_samples: downlink number of samples
- dl_buffer: downlink buffer size (transmission queue size)
- dl_tx_brat: transmitted bit rate from BS to UE
- dl_tx_pkts: number of packets transmitted from BS to UE
- dl_cqi: downlink Channel Quality Indicator

b) Action: At each decision step, the agent determines how to distribute the total number of PRBs available in the considered slices, n , mentioned in Table I. Taking into account the CoLORAN dataset, this will be done using the parameter “sum_granted_prbs” collected for each UE at each timestamp:

$$PRB_n = \sum_{m=1}^{N_{UE}} (sum_granted_prbs)_{n,m} \quad (1)$$

where $n = 1, \dots, N_{SL}$ indicates the slices and $m = 1, \dots, N_{UE}$ indicates the UEs in the slice.

Then grouped for each slice and finally divided by the total number of PRBs granted. So, the results will be a percentage allocation of all PRBs between slices, configuring a continuous set of actions.

$$Action_n = \frac{PRB_n}{\sum_{q=1}^{N_{SL}} PRB_q} \quad (2)$$

with $n, q = 1, \dots, N_{SL}$ indicating the number of slices.

Thus, the action vector containing the percentage allocated per slice will be constrained to:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{N_{SL}} Action_n = 1 \quad (3)$$

Note that from this per-slice allocation, the actual PRB assignment among the UEs follows the dataset predefined scheduling, which in this case is the Round-Robin policy.

Fig. 2: RL Agent with LLM-guidance workflow.

c) Reward: The reward at each time step t is formulated as a weighted combination of KPMs relevant to the different network slices: throughput for eMBB, latency for URLLC, and the number of packets transmitted for mMTC. It is expressed as:

$$R_t = \sum_{j=1}^N w_j \cdot r_j \quad (4)$$

w_j : are the slice priority factors that define the relative contribution of each metric, and as in (3) they are constrained to sum up to 1. This formulation follows the standard scalarization approach in multi-objective RL reward calculation and has been widely used, such as in [8], [18]. Note that the URLLC coefficient is negative because this encourages the agent to minimize latency, which is measured by the number of bytes in the transmission buffer, the smaller the buffer, the smaller the latency.

d) Next State: This is the state of the following timestamp, which in the dataset represents the next row.

C. RL Agent Workflow with LLM Enhancement

The proposed work considers the main workflow of the RL agent, enhanced with the LLM guidance presented in Fig. 2. The workflow begins by collecting and preprocessing the Colosseum dataset [22] to extract relevant KPMs, which are organized into observations, actions, and base KPMs for slice performance evaluation. Normalized observations and scaled actions are passed to the offline RL agent, while rewards are dynamically adjusted using slice weights generated by a pretrained LLM. At the start of each episode, an operator prompt specifies the prioritized slice, which the LLM interprets to produce reward weights as in Eq.(4). These weights are applied across all steps of the episode to compute the rewards from the collected offline data. After the episode, the RL policy is updated using the stored transitions. This process repeats for all episodes, enabling the agent to learn policies guided by LLM-informed priorities while capturing meaningful slice behavior over time. The overall steps of the proposed solution are described in Algorithm 1.

Fig. 3: Prompt structure example.

Slice priorities follow a predefined cyclic pattern: equal allocation at first, followed by prioritization of mMTC, URLLC, and eMBB; repeating until the end of all episodes.

Algorithm 1: LLM-Guided Offline RL

Input: CoLORAN dataset; Operator prompt template

- 1 Extract trajectories from CoLORAN dataset
- 2 Preprocess extracted data
- 3 Initialize the offline RL parameters (Tab. II)
- 4 **for** *Episodes* **do**
- 5 Generate episode-level operator prompt
- 6 Query LLM with prompt
- 7 Obtain reward weights from LLM output
- 8 **for** *Steps* **do**
- 9 Observe current state
- 10 Apply action using current RL policy
- 11 Retrieve next state from extracted data
- 12 Compute reward using LLM weights, Eq.(4)
- 13 Store transition (state, action, reward, next state)
- 14 **end**
- 15 Update RL policy using collected offline transitions
- 16 **end**

Output: Trained policy; Per-slice RL return

An organized prompt guides the LLM in generating the slice weights for the RL agent reward. This prompt includes the following components, also shown in Fig. 3:

- Objective: basic description of the context, goal, and operator choice for slice prioritization in the next episode.
- Environment information: aggregated information per slice of the just finished episode and the previous slice weight configuration.
- Constraints: limit of percentage distribution and guidance on output format.

TABLE II: Simulation Settings

Simulation Parameter	Value
# slices	3
# input feature per slice	6
# actions	3
# episodes	50
# steps per epoch	~ 2000
IQL Parameter	Value
Actor Learning Rate	0.0001
Critic Learning Rate	0.001
Batch size	256
Expectile	0.7
Target Network Synch. Coeff.	0.8
Discount factor	0.99

III. RESULTS

A. Parameters Setting

For implementation, a state of the art offline RL algorithm called Implicit Q-Learning (IQL) [23] has been chosen because it avoids querying the values of unseen actions while still being able to perform multi-step dynamic programming updates. And the d3rlpy library [24] was selected to execute the algorithm simulation in Python. The choice of LLM was made considering the limited computational resources available and the necessity for the model to comply with European legislation [25]. Given these constraints, Mistral 7B [26] was selected as the LLM component, which is a dense transformer-based model with approximately seven billion parameters and used with the quantization configuration Q4_K_M to compress the model and balance performance and resource usage. The model was deployed locally using Ollama [27], which enables efficient execution and integration within Python through its API. The simulation parameter settings decided for running the simulations and the hyper-parameters fine-tuned of the IQL algorithm are listed in Table II.

B. Simulated Results

1) Comparison Tests Description:

a) *LLM-based dynamic Test - Proposed Solution:* This is the proposed solution, and as previously described in this work, the priority weights are dynamically updated at the beginning of each episode based on the LLM interpretation of the operator prompt. This setup allows the reward design to adapt to changing priorities.

b) *Simple dynamic Test - Predefined Solution:* In this test, the reward weights vary over the episodes according to the deterministic cyclic schedule described above, producing a changing prioritization scheme without relying on adaptation or feedback. At each interval, the prioritized slice is assigned a reward weight of 0.6 while the other two slices are assigned with a reward coefficient of 0.2 each.

c) *CoLORAN static Test - CoLo Solution:* In this test, the slice priorities are set based on the default values presented in [8], and similarly to the previous scenario, these weights are kept equal for all episodes. For eMBB, mMTC and URLLC they are, respectively: 72.0440333, 0.229357798,

Fig. 4: Cumulative normalized return of RL agent for the three solutions vs number of steps.

0.00005 and are calculated using priority values and scaling factors (i.e., the maximum value for that specific slice KPM); for more details, see the referenced paper. Moreover, to be comparable with the other solutions, they are scaled to be in the range [0,1].

2) *Comparison Results:* The validation of the compared tests was performed using off-policy evaluation (OPE), a technique that estimates the performance of a trained policy using only offline data. Specifically, the Fitted Q Evaluation (FQE) method was employed to approximate the action-value function corresponding to the trained policy.

a) *Cumulative Return:* The global behavior of the solutions was analyzed using the cumulative normalized return aggregated across all network slices, which serves as an indicator of performance consistency, approximating how effectively the models distribute PRBs among the slices. As shown in Fig. 4, the proposed model has a steeper growth trend, ultimately reaching a higher cumulative reward than the other two baselines, supporting the findings that dynamically adjusting the reward weights through the LLM leads to more efficient learning performance. In contrast, the CoLo solution exhibits weaker performance growth because it relies on static priority weights that are kept constant throughout all episodes. Although this approach ensures stable behavior, it prevents the model from adapting its reward structure to changing slice demands, resulting in a lower cumulative reward compared to the proposed approach. Similarly, the Predefined solution demonstrates lower cumulative performance due to its simplified dynamic design. This lack of adaptive adjustment limits the ability to respond to system changes, leading to suboptimal resource allocation.

b) *Per-slice KPMs study:* The results in Fig. 5 compare the normalized returns across the three slice KPMs: eMBB throughput, mMTC packet transmission, and URLLC buffer size. The proposed solution achieves the highest return for mMTC and has a slightly better performance for

Fig. 5: Comparison of normalized returns for eMBB, mMTC, and URLLC slices across the three solutions.

eMBB, while ensuring favorable URLLC buffer behavior. The comparable eMBB return across solutions indicates that throughput-oriented objectives can be effectively satisfied even with static or predefined priorities. However, the Predefined solution shows reduced performance for mMTC due to its fixed, manually assigned reward weights, which limit its ability to adapt to varying traffic dynamics. The CoLo solution, while achieving the lowest URLLC buffer occupancy due to its latency-centric and static priority design, is biased toward URLLC and consequently underperforms in mMTC and does not effectively balance the requirements of different slices. In contrast, the proposed approach dynamically adapts reward priorities, enabling a more balanced optimization across slices and better overall performance.

c) *Priority KPMs study:* In this final analysis, summarized in Table III, the performance of the two dynamic solutions is evaluated under the cycling slice priority configurations. The table reports the mean normalized return for each slice during the episodes in which that slice is assigned the highest importance. It is evident that the proposed solution demonstrates dynamic behavior, with returns that adapt according to the prioritized slice without the weights being predetermined but created on demand based on the operator objective. In particular, the proposed solution achieves a better return for URLLC and eMBB slices when prioritized, while it is less effective for mMTC. Further analysis should be done to better understand why.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented an LLM-guided RL framework for inter-slice resource prioritization within the O-RAN architecture. In the proposed approach, the LLM operating in the Non-RT RIC receives operator prompts and contextual information, guiding the selection of coefficients that shape the reward function of the RL agent deployed in the Near-RT RIC. The RL agent then leverages these dynamically adjusted

TABLE III: Mean slice KPMs returns under different priority settings

	Priority	R_eMBB	R_mMTC	R_URLLC
Prop_Sol	URLLC	0.191890	0.362256	0.425341
	eMBB	0.643897	0.191592	0.177722
	equal	0.305546	0.297194	0.309167
	mMTC	0.285159	0.563370	0.220567
Pred_Sol	URLLC	0.196466	0.196466	0.589398
	eMBB	0.608116	0.202705	0.202705
	equal	0.319846	0.308601	0.308601
	mMTC	0.209856	0.629568	0.209856

rewards, together with local network observations, to make more efficient resource allocation. The results demonstrate that intelligent reconfiguration of reward weights through LLM prioritization significantly improves the cumulative return of the RL agent, while achieving stronger compliance with operator-defined objectives compared to static weighting schemes. Future work will focus on extending the framework in several directions, such as having a more detailed and fine-grained reward design, which could further enhance the interpretability and precision of the behavior of the RL agent. Moreover, deploying the proposed method in an online environment would enable real-time adaptation and validation under dynamic network conditions, particularly in scenarios with varying numbers of UEs and heterogeneous traffic demands; while also enriching the evaluation with additional networking KPIs at both per-slice and global levels to provide a clearer assessment of the practical impact. Finally, scaling the solution to guide multiple BSs simultaneously would enable a more comprehensive and coordinated O-RAN resource management strategy.

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